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*Digital Currency - Concept of Digital Bond
Exchange System in Loosely Coupled Mobile Systems*

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**Hochschule für Technik
und Wirtschaft Berlin**

University of Applied Sciences

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Nikhil Amin

Abstract

This thesis investigates the concept of a Digital Bond Exchange System, also referred to as an IOU in this paper, within loosely coupled mobile systems, focusing on their application as a localized currency. By examining various forms of money over 5000 years of history, this study examines the implications of an IOU in small, localized communities, without relying on blockchain technology. Employing a combined approach involving literature review and scenario analysis, a conceptual framework is proposed for implementing the IOU system, assessing its feasibility and potential advantages in localized communities. The research seeks to address key inquiries surrounding the viability of an IOU as a localized currency and strategies for their implementation without the intricate complexities associated with blockchain technology. Furthermore, it delves into the basics of digital cryptocurrencies, and the requisite technological components, including various cryptographic algorithms essential for the development of an IOU. Through an interdisciplinary lens, this study aims to offer insights into the practical application and implications of an IOU as a form of localized currency, shedding light on its potential role in contemporary economic landscapes.

1 Introduction

The study commences with an examination of diverse historical and contemporary currency systems on a global scale, analyzing their societal impacts. The research seeks to assess the potential of digital bonds as a localized currency system. Of particular interest is the examination of an alternative currency model tailored for small, localized communities, without relying on blockchain technology. Consequently, the study emphasizes the importance of evaluating the feasibility of such a system beyond theoretical considerations. This investigation intersects historical analysis of money, blockchain technology, cryptographic algorithms, local economic dynamics, and innovative digital currency framework. Methodologically, the research employs a combination of literature review and case scenario analysis to achieve its objectives.

1.1 Background and Motivation

This research aims to propose a conceptual framework for a Digital Bond Exchange System tailored particularly for local communities, driven by the acknowledgment of the shortcomings of traditional financial systems in meeting their needs. In such communities, conventional currencies and banking systems may prove impractical, necessitating the exploration of alternative solutions. By concentrating on this system, the research aims to bridge this gap by utilizing digital technologies that are not too complex to enable efficient value exchange. The impetus for this initiative lies in empowering individuals within local communities, granting them enhanced financial independence and adaptability in handling economic transactions. Additionally, the study intends to assess the feasibility and advantages of implementing a Digital Bond Exchange System, underscoring the importance of ensuring practicality and real-world benefits. To this end, scenarios have been developed to offer valuable insights into the feasibility and ramifications of adopting such a localized currency system.

1.2 Research questions

1. How can Bonds/IOUs be used as a localized form of currency?
2. How to implement such a localized currency without Blockchain technology?

1.3 Methodology

The methodology used to support the contents of this thesis includes two key components, which are:

1. **Literature research**

A comprehensive examination of existing literature on money, local currencies, blockchain technology, cryptography, algorithms, information security, and economic theories was conducted to understand the theoretical framework and historical context.

2. **Scenarios for Implementation** Two hypothetical scenarios were developed to explore the practical application and implications of using IOUs as a form of local currency within small communities, providing insights into their feasibility and potential benefits in real-world settings.

2 Fundamental concepts

2.1 What is Money?

Money is defined as something generally accepted as a medium of exchange, a measure of value, or a means of payment. Hence, from this definition, we understand that the foundation of money is based on trust. For anything to be of general acceptance can only be possible by trust. If people don't have trust that others will accept anything given to them as money, then they too won't accept that as a form of money [Byl04].

Money like any valuable item lacks intrinsic utility; its acceptance is based upon the assumption that others will recognize its value. In other words, its value depends on the importance that people place on it and it is socially accepted [Gra11].

2.2 History of Money

Money has been a part of human history as long as 5000 years in one form or the other [Gra11]. Long before the advent of contemporary monetary systems, human societies engaged in various modes of exchange. Traditional economics literature often references the Barter System as a predominant method of exchanging goods and services in ancient times. Under this system, individuals would directly trade commodities or services without the involvement of any central authority or external intermediary. Transactions occurred based on mutual agreement, with participants exchanging items or services if both parties perceived a tangible benefit from the exchange. The notion of the Barter system serving as a precursor to modern currency was initially posited by the 18th-century Scottish philosopher Adam Smith in his book, 'The Wealth of Nations'. But numerous prominent anthropologists hold different perspectives on the Barter system, contending that credit ¹ and trust-based systems were the original form of money, while Barter emerged later primarily in pre-industrialized societies where transactions occurred beyond a familiar cultural context [Gra11].

Various primitive forms of money emerged throughout history, each serving as a medium of exchange in different cultures and regions. Across the globe, commodities ranging from salt to tobacco have functioned as forms of currency at various points in time. The ancient Babylonians and Assyrians utilized barley for transactions. Almonds were utilized as money by natives in

¹Credit is defined as the ability of a person or an entity to obtain goods or services before payment, based on the trust that payment will be made in the future.

certain regions of India, while corn served as currency among Guatemalans. Mongolians used bricks of tea, and Norwegians adopted butter as a form of money. In parts of Southeast Asia, including the Philippines, Japan, and Burma, standardized measures of rice were employed as commodity money. Salt has been widely utilized as a form of currency throughout history, particularly in regions such as China, North Africa, and the Mediterranean [Ars22].

Then came the coins made of precious metals. Recent excavations conducted at Guanzhuang in Henan Province, China, have unearthed a bronze foundry dating back to the Eastern Zhou period (c. 770–220 BC). Noteworthy discoveries within the excavation include clay moulds specifically designed for the casting of spade coins. Examination of the technical attributes of these moulds by Dr. Zhao and co-authors from Zhengzhou University and Peking University provides evidence supporting the assertion that the Guanzhuang site operated as a mint dedicated to the production of standardized coins. By the use of radiocarbon dating techniques, it was indicated that the organized minting activities at Guanzhuang commenced between the years 640–550 BC. This makes Guanzhuang as the world’s oldest minting site, thereby contributing significant historical clarity to the evolution of coinage systems [Zha+21]. Money soon began to assume a dual nature, often navigating the boundaries of commodity and debt-token. This duality is exemplified by the use of coins, typically made of precious metals such as silver or gold, which possess inherent value yet acquire additional worth upon being minted with the emblem of a kingdom or of a local governing authority [Gra11].

The Age of Paper Money then arrived. The Yuan (1260–1368) dynasty was the first political regime in history to deploy paper money. Since then, throughout history, as several kingdoms and provinces turned into full-fledged countries, the use of coins and paper currency as a form of money still exists today [GPW22]. Commercial Banks ² trace their origins to medieval Italy, where goldsmiths began issuing warehouse receipts for deposited gold. Over time, these receipts evolved into the modern banking system. Meanwhile, Central Banks ⁽³⁾ emerged between the seventeenth and twentieth centuries to support and facilitate government economic activities, marking a significant development in the financial landscape [Bor21]. Each country or even a specific area can have its own form of money, which is called Currency. The most widely used currency in the world is US Dollars. During the late 19th century, several prominent global currencies followed a practice known as the

²Commercial Banks are profit-driven institutions that offer a wide range of financial services to individuals, businesses, and governments. They accept deposits, provide loans, facilitate payments, and offer various investment products.

³Central Banks are responsible for managing a country’s money supply, controlling interest rates, and maintaining financial stability.

'Gold Standard'. This international financial mechanism linked a nation's currency value to a specific quantity of gold, facilitating currency exchange across different nations. The Gold Standard persisted, in various forms, for approximately a century until its breakdown amidst the economic upheavals of the early 20th century. The onset of inflation during World War I compelled the UK and other nations to abandon the Gold Standard. A modified version was reintroduced in 1925, only to be dismantled once again in 1931 during the Great Depression. US President Richard Nixon ultimately terminated the USA's adherence to the Gold Standard in 1971. Subsequently, in 1976, the US Government revised the dollar's definition, eliminating all references to gold [JP15].

The past 20 years or so saw the emergence of a new form of the monetary system using the Internet. This mode of financial transaction is facilitated through the utilization of computer systems and portable electronic devices, exemplified by smartphones or tablet devices. In the preceding decade, Virtual currencies appeared which function as digital representations of money, and are stored and exchanged via computer programs or specialized software. We are currently in the age of digital money, which represents the electronic form of economic value.

2.3 Debt

Cambridge Dictionary defines Debt as something that is owed to someone else or the state of owing something. Debt is also defined as an exchange that has not been brought to completion [Gra11]. Throughout history, Debt has influenced morality, social relationships, and the rise of world religions. The history of debt can be traced back to the Mesopotamian civilization, where farmers were required to pay taxes to the wealthy. In those times, if a transaction couldn't be fulfilled, family members would be held as collateral. This was especially true during times of poor harvests, when vulnerable populations such as impoverished farmers, would accumulate debt to affluent neighbors or wealthy moneylenders. The consequences of such indebtedness resulted in the loss of land ownership, as individuals went from being landowners to becoming tenants on what was once their own property. The economic strain was so severe that even the children of those in debt faced dire consequences, including being enslaved within the households of creditors or, in more extreme cases, being subjected to foreign enslavement [Gra11].

In the modern world, the most common prevailing forms of debt include various loan arrangements such as personal loans, vehicle loans, home loans,

and also mortgages. In these arrangements, borrowers typically receive a pre-determined sum of money that must be repaid in its entirety by a specified future date, spanning months or years. Additionally, loan terms outline the interest rate, expressed as a percentage of the loan amount, which compensates the lender for assuming the associated risks.

2.4 Bonds

With the emergence of money, the system of financial bonds also originated. The first bond was issued on November 7, 1623, by Dutch East India Company. A bond is a document to recognize the presence of a debt. It is used as an instrument to borrow/lend money between a borrower and a lender. The lenders are also referred to as Investors which could either be individuals, accredited investors, or wealthy individuals and institutions. The borrower is referred to as a corporation, they make a promise to make payments back. The bond is a document that contains information regarding the money that the lender will receive back and when. There are a few important details that the bond contains such as the Face Value of the bond, Coupon Rate, and Date of Maturity. The face value is often equal to USD 1,000, while the coupon rate represents the interest rate the borrower is promising to pay to lenders. The coupon rate and the face value combined, determine the magnitude of Coupon Payments which is the interest payment. The date of maturity indicates the date on which the borrower must return the borrowed capital to the lenders. These 3 elements are fixed once the bond is issued and cannot be changed. The bond can however be sold to another party by the original borrower [Ros+18]. Hence, Bonds represent a form of debt instrument utilized by borrowers such as companies to secure funds from lenders such as investors, promising repayment along with accrued interest.

Numerous digital bond exchange systems currently exist in the financial landscape, with a majority leveraging blockchain technology. According to recent findings from the International Capital Market Association (ICMA), there are presently over 60 such systems globally, and this number is continually expanding [ICM24].

2.5 IOU

IOU which stands for 'I owe you' is a written promise to pay back a debt. IOUs can manifest in various formats, can consist both typed and handwritten expressions, with their content signed by either party involved [Invnd]. IOUs originated as informal agreements or commitments between two parties.

Over time, these informal IOUs transitioned into more structured systems adopted by businesses and governmental entities. They facilitated the extension of credit, enabling businesses to expand significantly while upholding trust among stakeholders.

In modern times, utility of IOUs have expanded further from traditional person-to-person lending or borrowing scenarios. IOUs now encompass a wide range of financial obligations, including bonds issued by corporations or government entities, which promise future payments along with interest. Consequently, Bonds can be viewed as a type of IOU. Nevertheless, it is essential to recognize that despite the evolution of IOUs over centuries, from simple handwritten notes to sophisticated digital contracts prevalent today, their fundamental essence remains unchanged. At its core, an IOU continues to signify a commitment made in the present for payment or fulfillment in the future.

At a fundamental level, an IOU may encompass essential details, such as the borrower's and lender's identities, the debt amount, the current date, the deadline for debt repayment, and the borrower's signature. Additionally, IOUs should specify the following [Invnd]:

- The method of debt repayment, and detailing whether it will be settled in a lump sum or through installments.
- A structured repayment plan outlining the size and frequency of payments, particularly applicable for installment-based repayments.
- The consideration of interest, including explicit details on the applicable interest rate if it is charged.
- Inclusion of a guarantor for the debt, if applicable.
- Designation of the state whose legal statutes govern the agreement.
- The signature of the lender and the borrower to authenticate the document.

2.6 How is Money created?

This section investigates four main ideas or schools of thought explaining where money comes from, who has the power to make it, and the rules that control its creation. We delve into these perspectives, shedding light on how they are used and why they are important when we talk about how money is made today [Hoo22].

2.6.1 Folk Tales

In the "Folk Tale" school of thought, money is conceptualized as a limited commodity and its value is tied to precious metals like gold. The premise suggests that the creation of money is attributed to the government or a public authority, subsequently flowing into banks. Once within the banking system, the narrative contends that banks possess the ability to lend money to individuals for diverse purposes such as purchasing goods or making investments. Moreover, the tale extends to suggest that even governmental bodies may borrow money from banks.

A central theme introduced in this narrative is the notion of a fractional reserve system. According to this concept, banks are perceived to lend out a substantial portion of the money deposited by customers. The rationale behind this approach is the understanding that individuals typically do not withdraw their entire deposits simultaneously, allowing banks to lend a significant fraction of these funds. The fractional reserve system is purported to serve a dual purpose: augmenting the overall money supply in circulation and enabling banks to generate additional revenue through interest earned on loans. The narrative implies that banks can accrue interest on lent funds, which would otherwise remain dormant in individuals' accounts. [Hoo22]

2.6.2 Neoclassical orthodoxy

A central concept in this school of thought is the "money multiplier" model of credit creation. According to this model, banks initially seek to attract deposits from savers, in accordance with the Folk Tale narrative. Subsequently, the Central Bank establishes the specific proportion of total customer deposits that Commercial Banks must retain, defining the share available for lending. This designated proportion termed a "reserve requirement," is usually around 10 percent. A lower reserve requirement implies that banks can allocate a greater portion of customers' deposits for lending, while a higher requirement restricts the proportion available for lending. The Central Bank, according to this theoretical framework, can thus influence the creation of new credit by regulating the mandatory deposit holdings of banks.

This view suggests that banks need customer deposits to create new loans, and it emphasizes banks as intermediaries between savers and borrowers. However, there is a limitation of this Neo-classical perspective, particularly the inability to explain the origin of the money that initiates the lending process. This discrepancy challenges the credibility of the money multiplier model in explaining the expansion of the money supply [Hoo22].

2.6.3 State-based money theories

In challenging the conventional neoclassical narrative surrounding the origins of money, a distinct cohort of thinkers assert an alternative perspective which is based on the theory of Chartalism, emerged in the 19th century from a German theorist Georg Knapp. Georg Knapp, a key proponent of Chartalism, argued that historically, it was the state or sovereign that undertook the initial creation of money within their mints. Subsequently, the state infused this newly created money into the economy to facilitate essential transactions, such as financing wars or compensating troops. In this narrative, money emanates from a deliberate state action of creation and expenditure. Moreover, to sustain the demand for this currency, the state mandated that individuals settle their taxes using it. Chartalists assert that contemporary money fundamentally operates as fiat currency, signifying a form of money devoid of backing from any tangible asset other than the authority of the state. However, recent clarifications asserts that banks, rather than governments, play a central role in the creation of new money pose a notable challenge to the Chartalist narrative [Hoo22].

2.6.4 Public-Private “deal”

This theory gives rise to an alternative perspective which combines ideas from the credit theory of money, which is essentially about how commercial banks create money and Chartalism. Money creation is perceived as a collaborative effort involving states and banks, similar to the neoclassical standpoint. Within this framework, commercial banks function as intermediaries between the government and institutional investors during government borrowing. Notably, it underscores that commercial banks play the pivotal role in creating new money entering individuals’ bank accounts. Diverging from conventional perspectives, banks do not wait for customer deposits before initiating loans; instead, the act of granting a loan generates a fresh deposit in the borrower’s account. Consequently, the inception of a new loan simultaneously results in the creation of fresh money in the customer’s account, decoupled from traditional deposit-taking processes [Hoo22].

2.7 Blockchain

Blockchain is as an unalterable ledger technology that facilitates decentralized transactions. It can be conceptualized as a public ledger where all transactions are permanently recorded in a series of blocks. This chain of series of blocks expands as new blocks are consistently added. To ensure user security and

ledger consistency, asymmetric cryptography ⁴ using Digital Signature and Distributed Consensus algorithms have been integrated into the Blockchain system [Zhe+17]. One of the well known applications of blockchain technology is the cryptocurrency Bitcoin.

A node within a blockchain denotes a computational device actively engaged in a peer-to-peer network, contributing computing power to the network. The blockchain network constitutes a collection of such nodes implementing a specific blockchain peer-to-peer protocol. This network operates in a fully federated, decentralized, and distributed manner, with all nodes collaboratively orchestrated and coordinated. The primary responsibility of a blockchain node is to ascertain the correctness and validity of information within a block, storing the accurate data. In accordance with their functions within the blockchain network, nodes can be broadly categorized into three types [Xio+22]:

1. **Broadcast Nodes:** These nodes exclusively transmit transaction information while accepting a limited amount of blockchain data.
2. **Complete Nodes:** These nodes store the entire blockchain information and perform various functions such as initiating transactions, propagating transactions, and verifying data consistency.
3. **Mining Nodes (Miners):** Nodes equipped with substantial computing power to generate new blocks and broadcast transactions. They play a pivotal role in supporting the stable and efficient operation of the blockchain system.

This classification reflects the diverse roles and functionalities that nodes fulfill in ensuring the integrity and functionality of the blockchain system [Xio+22].

Key characteristics of Blockchain technology [Zhe+17]

1. **Decentralization:** Blockchain eliminates the need for a trusted central system such as a central financial institution, in turn eliminating the associated costs and performance bottlenecks at the central servers. Instead, it leverages consensus algorithms to uphold data consistency across a distributed network.

⁴Asymmetric cryptography, also known as Public key cryptography uses a pair of keys; a public key, which is known publicly, and a private key, which is known only by its owner. A message encrypted by one of the keys can be decrypted only by the paired key [HN17]

2. **Persistence:** Transaction validation occurs promptly, and the acceptance of invalid transactions can be restricted. Once transactions are incorporated into the blockchain, their deletion or rollback is exceedingly challenging. The immediate identification of blocks containing invalid transactions is possible within the blockchain system.
3. **Anonymity:** Each user possesses the capability to engage with the blockchain through a uniquely generated address, ensuring the confidentiality of their actual identity.
4. **Auditability:** The verification and tracking of transactions within the Blockchain are straightforward.

Blockchain's capacity to facilitate transactions without the need for banks or intermediaries makes it applicable in diverse financial services, encompassing digital assets, remittance, and online payments. Furthermore, the versatility of blockchain extends to its integration into other domains, including smart contracts ⁵, public services, the Internet of Things, and security services. [Zhe+17]

Current blockchain systems are categorized roughly into three types: public blockchain, private blockchain and consortium blockchain. In public blockchain, all records are visible to the public and everyone could take part in the consensus process. In a consortium blockchain, only a group of pre-selected nodes would participate in the consensus process. As for private blockchain, only those nodes that come from one specific organization would be allowed to join the consensus process. The main difference among the three types of blockchains is that public blockchain is decentralized, consortium blockchain is partially centralized and private blockchain is fully centralized as it is controlled by a single group [Zhe+17].

Disadvantages of Blockchain

- Scalability is a major disadvantage in blockchain systems, particularly as transaction volumes surge over time. The increasing number of transactions contributes to the bulkiness of the blockchain, as each node must store all transactions for validation purposes. This necessity arises from the need to verify whether the source of a given transaction has been previously spent or remains unspent. Additionally, the original constraints on block size and the time required to generate new blocks limit the

⁵Smart contract is a computer program or protocol that runs on a blockchain and executes the terms of an agreement between parties automatically when certain conditions are met.

throughput of the Bitcoin blockchain to around 7 transactions per second. Consequently, this capacity falls short of meeting the demand for processing millions of transactions in real-time [Zhe+17].

- Privacy leakage in blockchain technology is another significant concern despite the inherent anonymity provided by public and private keys. While users transact with their keys without revealing their true identities, the transparency of blockchain exposes transactional details and balances associated with public keys. Recent research has demonstrated the potential for identifying users through their Bitcoin transactions, undermining transactional privacy [Zhe+17].
- Selfish Mining, a known vulnerability in blockchain systems, involves colluding miners seeking to exploit the network for personal gain. Selfish miners withhold their mined blocks instead of immediately broadcasting them. Only under specific conditions will they reveal their private branch to the public. Since the private branch tends to be longer than the existing public chain, other miners accept it. Consequently, honest miners waste resources on an obsolete branch while selfish miners continue mining on their private chain unhindered by competition, thereby aiming to maximize their profits [Zhe+17].

Architecture of Blockchain

Blockchain is a sequence of blocks or a chained data structure, where distinct data blocks are interconnected based on their generation time in ascending order. Each block in the chain comprises a collection of transaction data, composed of a block header and a block body. The block header and body together constitute a data block. Each block in the sequence possesses a singular parent block, with the block header incorporating the hash of the preceding block. The initial block in the blockchain is referred to as the genesis block, distinguished by its lack of a parent block [Xio+22]. Figure 1 shows the Architecture of Blockchain technology.

Specifically, the block header encompasses: [Xio+22]

1. **Version:** This parameter tracks software or protocol updates.
2. **PrevBlock Hash:** The current block includes the hash value of the preceding block. The hash is generated irreversibly through a hash algorithm, creating a unique and fixed-length value that distinctly identifies the block. Storing the hash value of the previous block in the current block ensures a linkage between the two.

Figure 1: Blockchain Architecture

3. **Merkle Root:** This records the hash value of the Merkle tree root for the block.
4. **Timestamp:** The creation timestamp of the block is documented. This timestamp ensures the sequential storage of blockchain data based on the block's recorded generation time, facilitating the traceability of data sources within the chain.
5. **Difficulty Target:** This represents the difficulty coefficient that needs to be solved for the current block.
6. **Nonce:** an 4-byte field calculated by the node using computational power, the nonce is generally a value smaller than the specified target.

The block body serves as the repository for transaction content and associated information. Each transaction entry contains a digital signature which is used to protect the integrity of the block data. In the blockchain, all transaction information undergoes processing within the Merkle tree structure located in the block body. The transaction details find their place in the leaf nodes of the Merkle tree which are paired through hash calculations and combined, generating a hash value that extends up to the root node of the Merkle tree. Nodes across the entire network can access transaction information on the tree node. The hash value of the Merkle tree root reflects the collective node information of the entire network and becomes altered if any transaction

information is tampered with maliciously. The Merkle tree structure provides a certain level of security for the blockchain [Xio+22]. At its core, a Merkle tree is essentially a hierarchical arrangement of hash values. It starts with a set of concrete data, represented as Merkle leaves, progresses through intermediate hashes (Merkle branches), and culminates in the Merkle root—a singular hash value that encapsulates all the data. A sample representation of a Merkle tree structure is shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Merkle Tree Structure

The operation of blockchain follows three main stages: block creation, consensus verification, and ledger maintenance. Firstly, in the block creation stage, nodes on the blockchain network gather transaction details and compete to generate new blocks using their computing power. Nodes that successfully create blocks are rewarded according to the blockchain protocol’s incentive mechanism, often with economic benefits, encouraging them to contribute computing power consistently. Secondly, in the consensus verification stage, the node responsible for block creation broadcasts the newly created block to the entire network. All nodes in the network receive and verify numerous blocks, ensuring the accuracy of their content through a consensus algorithm. The verified data is then recorded in the blockchain ledger. Lastly, in the ledger management phase, nodes store the verified data for an extended period and conduct retrospective checks using timestamps and hash values stored in the block. This enables upper-layer applications to access ledger information through a query interface. Throughout these stages, nodes continuously pro-

vide computing power, ensuring the blockchain remains decentralized, open, stable, trustworthy, and transparent [Xio+22].

2.8 Digital Signatures

A digital signature is similar to a handwritten signature, albeit employing digital means rather than traditional pen and paper. Digital signatures operate on the principles of cryptography utilizing private and public key encryption techniques [Pat+19]. Digital signature infrastructures serve several key objectives. Firstly, messages authenticated using a digital signature offer recipients assurance regarding the authentic source of the message, confirming it originated from the purported sender. Secondly, they guarantee that the message's content remains unaltered throughout its transmission from sender to recipient, thereby enhancing data integrity along the communication pathway. Lastly, non-repudiation by the signer ensures that signers cannot deny their signature on data, reinforcing accountability and trust in digital transactions [Lin23].

Digital signature algorithms rely on a combination of two major concepts, public key cryptography and hashing functions. Every user possesses a set of private and public keys. The private key is to be held in strict confidentiality while the public key can be distributed to other users. The digital signature process typically comprises two phases: the signing phase and the subsequent verification phase [Zhe+17].

Consider the following that describes the signing and the verification phase in detailed steps. Figure 3 illustrates the same [Lin23].

If a Sender wants to digitally sign a message they are sending to Receiver, they perform the following actions:

1. Sender generates a message digest (i.e. hash)⁶ of the original plaintext message using one of the cryptographically sound hashing algorithms.
2. Sender then encrypts only the message digest using their private key. This encrypted message digest is called the digital signature.
3. Sender appends the signed message digest to the plaintext message.
4. Sender transmits the appended message to the Receiver.

⁶Hash, also referred to as message digests, is a super-condensed representation of a message's content, generated through a Hashing algorithm. We discuss the Hashing algorithm in Section 4.3.1.

When Receiver receives the digitally signed message, they reverse the procedure, as follows:

1. The Receiver decrypts the digital signature using the Sender's public key.
2. Receiver uses the same hashing algorithm to create a message digest of the full plaintext message received from Sender.
3. Receiver then compares the decrypted message digest they received from Sender with the message digest they computed themselves. If the two digests match, they can be assured that the message they received was sent by the Sender. If they do not match, either the message was not sent by Sender or the message was modified while in transit.

Figure 3: Digital Signature - Signing and Verifying

2.9 Digital Certificates

Digital certificates are pivotal in establishing confidence among parties engaged in communication by ensuring the authenticity of the individuals involved. These certificates essentially serve as authenticated representations of a person's public key, acting as a digital portrayal of their identity. Enclosed within a digital certificate is the public key, along with details about its owner and the entity associated with the certificate. This association binds a public key to a specific person or object, affirming their identity.

The authenticity of a digital certificate can be verified by anyone, thereby instilling trust in the certificate and its associated identity. By confirming

that a certificate has been signed by a trusted authority or entity, users can rely on the validity and genuineness of the associated public key. The utilization of digital certificates is essential for establishing trust and facilitating secure communication in diverse scenarios. The formulation of digital certificates aligns with the international standard X.509, which governs their structure and content. This standard ensures consistency and compatibility across various systems and applications. X.509-compliant certificates encompass a comprehensive array of data, furnishing vital information about the certificate itself and the entity it represents [Hug22].

Certificates conforming to the X.509 standard encapsulate the subsequent details [Hug22]:

1. **Subject Distinguished Name:** Identifies uniquely a person, device, or computer.
2. **Issuer Distinguished Name:** Uniquely identifies the Certification Authority that issued the certificate.
3. **128-bit serial number.**
4. **ValidFrom:** Commencement date and time.
5. **ValidTo:** Expiry date and time.
6. **Public key.**
7. **Key Usage Flags:** Including digital signature and key encipherment.
8. **Enhanced Key Usage Flags:** Such as Server Authentication, Client Authentication, and Email Security.
9. **URL of the Certificate Revocation List (CRL):** Associated with the particular certificate.
10. **URL of the OCSP (Online Certificate Status Protocol) ⁷ server:** Associated with the particular certificate (if available).
11. **Digital signature:** Generated by the Certification Authority at the time of issuance using their signing private key, encompassing all preceding information.

⁷Online Certificate Status Protocol (OCSP) is an Internet protocol used for obtaining the revocation status of an X.509 digital certificate.

Public Key Infrastructure (PKI)

The collective assembly of equipment, legal agreements, and trusted processes essential for securely issuing and managing digital certificates is known as a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI). Understanding PKI necessitates a grasp of digital certificates, as they are the primary entities managed and issued within this framework [Hug22]. However, the Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) is widely used across the globe. It was designed with trust as a fundamental principle. Its cryptographic framework is robust, delineating clear roles for each participant, and supported by mature hardware and widely utilized application program interfaces (APIs) ⁸ [SHC19].

From a technical perspective, a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) serves as a security framework responsible for generating and overseeing digital certificates to facilitate the application of asymmetric-key cryptography. This infrastructure comprises several components, notably a Certification Authority (CA), which issues digital certificates to requesting entities or subjects, binding their public key to their identity. Additionally, a Registration Authority (RA) plays a role in validating the identities of these end entities. Furthermore, a secured repository is utilized to store and distribute digital certificates, along with maintaining Certificate Revocation Lists (CRLs) which consist of the serial numbers of digital certificates issued by a CA that have been revoked, accompanied by the precise date and time of revocation. Lastly, a Certification Policy (CP) outlines the certification rules. Certificate authorities may revoke digital certificates due to reasons such as compromise, erroneous issuance, changes in certificate details, or alterations in security associations. The primary functions of a PKI consist of identity authentication and digital certification, serving as a foundational element for various applications reliant on public key cryptography, particularly for authentication and certification purposes, such as digital signatures [HN17].

2.10 Cryptocurrency

Cryptocurrencies had gained worldwide attention from investors, regulators, and the media, particularly since the introduction of Bitcoin by Nakamoto in a research paper in 2008. These digital currencies operate as peer-to-peer electronic cash systems, enabling direct online payments between parties without the involvement of any traditional financial institutions, hence making them completely decentralized systems. A distinctive feature of cryptocurrencies is their detachment from any higher authority, devoid of physical representation,

⁸The Application Programming Interface (API) serves as a software-to-software interface, establishing the terms for communication between applications across a network without requiring user intervention [De23].

and setting them apart from the majority of other financial assets [Cor+19].

In contrast to conventional financial assets, the value of cryptocurrencies is not tied to tangible assets, a country's economy, or a specific firm. Instead, their value is intricately linked to the security of an algorithm that meticulously traces all transactions. The increasing adoption of cryptocurrencies was attributed to their low transaction costs, decentralized peer-to-peer system, and absence of government control [Cor+19].

2.11 Bitcoin

One of the well-known applications of blockchain technology is the cryptocurrency Bitcoin which was the first cryptocurrency. The concept was introduced in October 2008 through a renowned white paper by a pseudonymous figure Satoshi Nakamoto and its open-source implementation was released in 2009 [KKO17]. The idea behind the concept was to create an electronic payment system based on cryptographic proof rather than trust, allowing parties to be involved in transactions directly instead of a trusted third party such as centralized financial institution. The primary objective of this concept was to mitigate the double spending issue by employing a peer-to-peer distributed timestamp server, which generates computational proof of the chronological order of transactions [Nak08].

Transaction

Transactions in a Bitcoin is performed by digital coins, which are represented as a chain of digital signatures. The below diagram illustrates a mechanism through which the owner of such a digital coin can transfer ownership to another individual by establishing a sequence or chain of digital signatures. This process operates by first performing a digital signature of the hash of the previous transaction and the public key of the next owner, then this digital signature is appended to the end of the coin. Consider Figure 4 below with three blocks. Let's assume that the first block in Figure 4 is owned by Alice and she wants to transfer this to Bob. It would be done by performing a hash of the entire first block and Bob's public key together. By doing this, Bob's public key is linked to the previous block. This hash is then signed by Alice's private key. Bob can decrypt the signature by using Alice's public key, thus verifying that it was indeed signed by Alice [Nak08].

Figure 4: Transaction

All transactions in Bitcoin are public but names are not attached to transactions. However, a strategy to safeguard privacy would be to disrupt the flow of information through the anonymous nature of public keys. While the public can observe the transfer of funds between parties, the transaction remains unlinkable to specific individuals. To enhance privacy further, employing a distinct key pair for each transaction serves as an additional protective measure, preventing the association of multiple transactions with a common owner. Despite these efforts, some degree of linkage is inevitable in multi-input transactions, as they inherently expose that their inputs shared the same owner. The potential risk arises when the identity of a key owner is disclosed, potentially unveiling other transactions associated with the same proprietor. This underscores the importance of considering privacy concerns, especially in situations where the disclosure of key ownership could inadvertently reveal additional transactions [Nak08].

Timestamp Server

The process described in the previous section has some issues such as, there is no way to know if any of the owners duplicate the digital coins along the way or in other words, the owners did not perform double spending. This could possibly happen if an owner has digitally signed one coin more than once and issued it to multiple other users. The problem of double spending can be avoided in a centralized system where a trusted third party such as Bank or a financial institution is aware of all transactions and therefore it could identify if a coin was spent second time. But in a decentralized system such

as Bitcoin, the challenge of double-spending is addressed by the mechanism of Timestamp server [Nak08].

The operational mechanism of Timestamp server involves the establishment of a sequential series of hashed data blocks, which is then published to everyone which serves as evidence of the existence of data within each block at a specific point in time. Consider a list of transactions (denoted as Tx) contained within a block and there is a need to validate their existence at a precise date. These transactions are incorporated with the hash of the preceding block and collectively hashed. This process continues further as subsequent blocks are added, forming an interconnected chain. The chain is published to everyone to ensure visibility within the network, enabling all participants to access the hashes. Consequently, any attempt by anyone to modify a transaction within a block would result in a distinct hash value for the block, resulting in a domino effect altering the hashes of all subsequent blocks. This inherent interdependence among blocks serves as a safeguard against tampering, as any alteration in a single transaction triggers an alteration in the entire chain, thereby preserving the integrity and immutability of the ledger [Nak08]. This is illustrated in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Timestamp Server

Proof of Work (PoW) Algorithm

Proof of Work is the algorithm officially used in Bitcoin for consensus verification. In order to establish a distributed timestamp server on a peer-to-peer basis, a Proof of Work Algorithm is utilized. This proof-of-work concept consists of an exploration of such a value that, when hashed with algorithm such as SHA-256, generates the hash value that should begin with a predetermined number of zero bits. The computational effort required for this task is exponentially proportional to the specified number of zero bits, and its validity can be verified through a single hash operation. Within the timestamp network, proof-of-work mechanism is used by iteratively incrementing a nonce⁹ in the

⁹Nonce is a cryptographic term that refers to an input value that remains unique within a specified context and does not repeat [SJC21]

block until a hash value is identified that has the right amount of zero bits needed to be accepted into the bitcoin network [Nak08]. This is what crypto mining refers to and one has to keep on performing the hash operation with a nonce repeatedly until one gets the hash value meeting the requisite zero bits. As shown in Figure 6 below, consider a block containing Transactions, a concept discussed in the preceding section. These Transactions, denoted as Tx, constitute the essential components of the block. Subsequently, all the Transactions within the block, alongside the hash of the preceding block and a Nonce value, undergo a process of hashing.

Figure 6: Proof Of Work

As mentioned above, the resultant hash must conform to a predetermined criterion that the hash must commence with a specified number of zero bits. However, achieving the requisite number of zero bits in the hash may not be attained in the initial hashing step. Consequently, an iterative approach is adopted whereby the Nonce value is systematically incremented, and the hashing process is reiterated. This iterative process necessitates the utilization of CPU power to execute the hashing computations. Through successive iterations, the Nonce value is adjusted until the desired hash with the requisite number of zero bits is generated. The Flowchart for the process described is illustrated in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Proof Of Work Algorithm Flowchart

The reason for following this iterative process of systematically incrementing a nonce is to make it difficult to alter transactions because any change in the ledger will change the hash. Obtaining a nonce value requires significant computational resources. Once all the work is done to find the nonce that generates the requisite number of zero bits and complete the proof-of-work, any attempt to change a block in the ledger would require doing all that work again, which means that the only way to change the block is by redoing all

the work to compute this hash. As subsequent blocks are linked to it in a chain, modifying the block would mean redoing the work for all the subsequent blocks.

Proof of Work (PoW) Algorithm is a consensus mechanism of Bitcoin. Therefore, only the node that successfully discovers the nonce value meeting the specified condition can accurately record the transaction and also receive the associated rewards. Upon receiving the broadcasted solution from this node, other nodes cease their attempts to solve the block puzzle but engage in verifying the integrity of the block information [Xio+22]. The proof-of-work mechanism is a way to make sure that decisions in the Bitcoin network are fair and secure. Instead of letting one person control the decision-making, every node within the network is granted equal participation rights. Each node's influence in the decision-making process is determined by the computational effort exerted by its CPU.

Modifying a past block requires an attacker to recompute the proof-of-work for the particular block and all subsequent blocks, subsequently catching up with and surpassing the work accomplished by the honest nodes. Subsequent blocks added to the chain exponentially diminish the likelihood of a slower attacker catching up. To adapt to changes in hardware speed and node participation levels, the proof-of-work difficulty is dynamically adjusted using a moving average, aiming for a specific average number of blocks generated per hour. If the block generation rate becomes too fast, the difficulty level increases accordingly [Nak08].

Network

In the traditional centralized system, a financial institutions declares that the transactions are authentic. However, in Bitcoin, transactions are broadcasted to everyone, who then agree that the transaction is legitimate. In such a decentralized system, a network is made up of nodes and a node refers to a computer run by anybody having enough computing power on their computer.

The following shows how the Network operates:-

1. Firstly, all new transactions are publicly announced.
2. These are then collected into blocks.
3. Every node in the network initiates the search for a challenging proof-of-work specific to the block i.e. to find the right hash with the right amount of zero bits in front of it.

4. When a node successfully discovers a proof-of-work, it broadcasts the block to all other nodes.
5. Confirm acceptance of the block by nodes only if all contained transactions are valid and have not been previously spent.
6. Manifest acknowledgment of the block's acceptance by nodes through the creation of the subsequent block in the chain, utilizing the hash of the accepted block as the preceding hash.

When a node successfully discovers a proof-of-work, it broadcasts the block to all other nodes, prompting them to verify its accuracy. Upon successful verification, each node retains a copy of the transaction. Subsequently, every node maintains an ongoing record of transactions, forming a chain as each transaction is linked to the previous one. However, in instances where two different versions are broadcasted, both ledgers are saved until one of them becomes longer. This complexity introduces a safeguard against double spending, the act of duplicating a digital coin. Consider a scenario where Alice attempts to double spend a digital coin. This leads to the existence of two distinct ledgers featuring the same transaction. The second ledger which has the duplicate transaction has to keep up with the first ledger since each transaction necessitates the generation of a challenging hash. Eventually, the duplicate ledger would not be able to catch up. The inherent principle retained in this context asserts that the correctness of the blockchain is determined by the length of its chain, with the longest chain being considered the accurate representation of the transaction history.[Nak08]. It requires a lot of computing power and electricity to come with the prerequisite hash that has the right amount of zero bits.

The advantage of this entire system is that it offers benefits that make the network stronger. Upon the initiation of the protocol with the initial block in the blockchain, other nodes are incentivized to participate and propagate the network, as this activity enables them to acquire digital coins. As more members join and contribute computing power and electricity to mine new coins, they are rewarded with digital coins. This creates an incentive for everyone to maintain the network's integrity and honesty. [Nak08].

2.12 Consensus Algorithms

Blockchain is fundamentally a distributed ledger comprising blocks with a defined structure. The data blocks are chronologically stored, and cryptographic techniques are employed for encryption and verification to ensure the integrity of the stored data, preventing tampering or forgery. Consensus algorithms play a crucial role in both appending new data blocks to the

blockchain and updating existing data, ensuring the reliability of the overall system. Consensus Algorithms aims to achieve consensus among blockchain nodes. Furthermore, the blockchain consensus algorithm must also prioritize considerations of security, scalability, resource consumption, and performance efficiency. Consensus algorithms in a blockchain network are categorized into non-Byzantine fault-tolerant algorithms and Byzantine fault-tolerant algorithms based on the consideration of the existence of malicious nodes [Xio+22].

2.12.1 Non-Byzantine Consensus Algorithms

Non-Byzantine Consensus Algorithms find primary application in enclosed environments characterized by a certain degree of isolation and a relatively high level of trust among nodes. Some of the non-Byzantine algorithms are the VR (Viewstamped Replication) algorithm, Paxos algorithm and Raft algorithm. However, there are drawbacks to Non-Byzantine Consensus Algorithms. In scenarios where malicious nodes engage in activities such as data tampering, Non-Byzantine Consensus algorithms face challenges in ensuring data security and system stability. Consequently, the applicability of Non-Byzantine Consensus algorithms becomes constrained when deployed in open networks featuring diverse nodes and lower levels of mutual trust [Xio+22].

2.12.2 Byzantine Consensus Algorithms

As Blockchain contains a network of distributed systems, achieving consensus among untrustworthy nodes presents a variation of the Byzantine Generals (BG) Problem. As per the Byzantine Generals Problem, a group of separate army generals commanding different segments of the Byzantine army surround a city. Some generals advocate for an attack and others for a retreat. However, the success of the attack depends on a unanimous decision, and only a unified front can help attain victory. Consequently, the generals must navigate the challenge of reaching a consensus on whether to attack or retreat. Yet, some generals may be traitors with the intent of thwarting agreement among the loyal generals. To address this challenge, an algorithm is essential to ensure the following conditions [LSP19]:

- All the loyal generals agree on the same plan of action: This means that even if there are some traitors among the generals trying to disrupt the plan, the algorithm should make sure that the loyal generals stick to the agreed-upon plan. No matter what the traitors do, the algorithm should ensure that the loyal generals follow the plan.
- The plan agreed upon by the loyal generals should be a good one: It's not enough for everyone to agree; they need to agree on a plan that

makes sense. The algorithm should prevent a small number of traitors from convincing the loyal generals to adopt a bad plan. The objective is to ensure that a small fraction of traitors cannot cause the adoption of an unfavorable plan by the loyal generals.

Byzantine failures, a significant concern in distributed network environments, refers to the challenge of achieving cooperative consensus among distributed nodes, where malicious nodes may exist. Within the context of blockchain technology, an issue may arise from the possibility that individual components within a blockchain network may engage in arbitrary or malicious behaviors, potentially collaborating with other faulty components. As a result, these actions can compromise the accuracy of node calculations within the blockchain, undermining the integrity and reliability of the system [LSP19].

The challenge of consensus in a distributed environment extends to blockchain, where the absence of a central node overseeing ledger uniformity across distributed nodes adds complexity. In this decentralized network, ensuring consistency among ledgers in different nodes becomes a formidable task. Protocols are essential within the blockchain framework to establish and maintain a consensus, addressing the unique challenges posed by its distributed nature. The Bitcoin system uses the POW (Proof of Work) consensus algorithm proposed by Markus Jakobsson, which takes into account the presence of malicious nodes in a blockchain. Few other Byzantine algorithms include PBFT (Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance) Algorithm, the PoS (Proof of Stake) consensus algorithm, DPoS (Delegated Proof of Stake) algorithm, PoH Algorithm (Proof of Humanity) and CW-PoW (Compute and Wait in the PoW) consensus algorithm. We shall describe PBFT (Practical Byzantine Fault-Tolerance) Algorithm and PoS (Proof-of-Stake) Algorithm in this paper.

1. **PBFT (Practical Byzantine Fault-Tolerance) Algorithm**

The primary focus of the PBFT algorithm lies in addressing transaction ordering issues within distributed nodes susceptible to Byzantine errors. It ensures consistency among non-Byzantine nodes in the system even when up to one-third of the nodes exhibit Byzantine behavior. Nodes in the PBFT algorithm include the master node and other peer nodes. The system autonomously selects the master node, responsible for distributing and processing information across the blockchain network and verifying its validity [Xio+22].

Assuming $3f + 1$ nodes in the PBFT algorithm's operation, with 1 master node, $2f$ honest nodes, and f malicious nodes, the algorithm's operation is divided into three phases: pre-preparation, preparation, and

submission. In the pre-preparation phase, the master node dispatches assigned sequence numbers and pre-preparation information to other nodes. As these nodes confirm receipt, the preparation phase commences. Each node broadcasts preparation information to all nodes, excluding itself. Once each node collects $2f + 1$ pieces of information, indicating readiness, the confirmation phase initiates. All nodes broadcast confirmation messages to the entire network. Once each node accumulates $2f + 1$ confirmation messages, the confirmation phase concludes, and the correct log information is returned and recorded in the blockchain. Figure 8 below illustrates the workflow of PBFT Algorithm.

As long as the number of Byzantine nodes remains below $1/3$ of the total, the PBFT consensus algorithm operates accurately, ensuring the blockchain system's reliability and substantially improving security performance. Figure 8 illustrates the workflow of a PBFT consensus algorithm [Xio+22].

Figure 8: PBFT Algorithm Workflow

2. PoS (Proof-of-Stake) Algorithm

The Proof of Stake (PoS) algorithm introduces the notion of tokens, utilizing them to designate the node with the highest stake in the system as the accounting node. This stake is calculated based on the quantity and duration of tokens held by a node. Nodes possessing more tokens and holding them for extended periods accrue higher equity. Elevated equity correlates with reduced mining difficulty, enhancing the efficiency of discovering the target value of a random number. Upon successfully obtaining the block's accounting right, the node's stake is reset, initiating the next round of stake accumulation.

A key advantage of the PoS algorithm lies in its elimination of the intricate mining process, relying solely on proof of stake for securing the accounting right. This streamlined approach reduces block time, transaction processing time, and significantly expedites consensus, thereby enhancing efficiency. Additionally, the PoS algorithm economizes and enhances the utilization of computing resources compared to the Proof of Work (PoW) algorithm [Xio+22].

2.13 Stablecoins

A Stablecoin represents a type of payment token whose value is tethered to an external asset outside the realm of cryptocurrency, typically a fiat currency such as the U.S. dollar or euro. Generally, the Stablecoin token is either fully or partially backed by this external asset, with an assurance from the issuer that it can be exchanged for the referenced asset at any given time. An analogy can be drawn to the early forms of paper notes issued by banks or central banks, which were backed by gold and promised to provide equivalent value in gold upon presentation to the bank. Stablecoins address the volatility issue associated with cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, making it simpler for individuals to conduct transactions in fiat currency-denominated goods using crypto-assets and facilitating cross-border transfers without concerns about price fluctuations. They offer numerous advantages for traders, allowing them to transition from volatile crypto-assets to Stablecoins seamlessly without exiting the cryptocurrency ecosystem. Moreover, Stablecoins are beneficial for the general public, particularly in facilitating cross-border payments. They enable instantaneous money transfers between users worldwide, often with minimal transaction fees. It's worth noting that while many Stablecoin tokens utilize fiat currency as their reference asset, some opt for physical commodities like gold instead. Stablecoins can be categorized into three main types: fiat-collateralized, crypto-collateralized, and non-collateralized [Ars22].

- Fiat-collateralized stablecoins typically maintain a fixed value in fiat currency, allowing holders to redeem them for the equivalent amount on demand. This category is the most prevalent in the market, with issuers expected to hold real-world fiat currency reserves off-chain and issue tokens representing these reserves, usually in a 1:1 ratio. This setup assures holders that the stablecoin can be redeemed for the corresponding asset or reserve.
- Crypto-collateralised stablecoins are backed by other cryptocurrencies.
- Non-collateralized stablecoins are still in experimental phases and lack asset backing. Instead, they depend on mathematical mechanisms to

maintain price stability. This is achieved by algorithmically adjusting the coin supply to counterbalance fluctuations in coin demand.

2.14 Local Currency

Local currencies or Community currencies belong to the category of complementary currencies, termed so because they operate in complement to a primary currency, thereby contributing to an additional economic benefits. Within this classification, community currencies stand out by their primary objective of fostering more equal, interconnected, and sustainable societies within a distinct and specified group. The classification of such a group may involve various criteria, including geographic boundaries or specific ecological and social goals [Zel20].

Local currencies vary in their structures and requirements. Some local currencies necessitate collateral which means that the individuals must exchange national currency to acquire the local currency. Conversely, others operate on a mutual credit system, leveraging peer pressure as a social collateral mechanism. In this system, members extend transferable loans to one another without interest. Typically confined to specific geographic areas, local currencies are limited to a designated group that accepts them as a supplementary medium of exchange. Since local currencies are often non-convertible, including into the official national currency, they remain within their defined region of validity and do not experience scarcity. Consequently, they can complement existing currencies by providing consistent liquidity or serving as an additional form of money supply, particularly in scenarios where the official currency's supply is insufficient [Zel20].

Local currencies have the potential to foster exchange systems that contribute to sustainable development, offering avenues for change through economic, environmental, and social pathways. The economic pathway suggests several dimensions. Firstly, local currencies are anticipated to serve as tools for enhancing local value and preventing economic leakage, thus stimulating localized economic activity and generating a local multiplier effect. Secondly, these schemes may provide a means of recognizing and valuing non-market activities, such as informal work and skills exchange. Thirdly, they can serve as a mechanism for financially marginalized individuals to access goods and services, while also facilitating trade among local businesses that are perceived as being more supportive of the community [JH18].

The social pathway is often regarded as the primary objective of local currency systems. They can incentivize neighborly support, foster trust among

the community members, enable participation by marginalized social groups, and underscore the value of skills beyond those recognized in the labor market [JH18].

Lastly, the environmental pathway highlights the potential contribution of local currencies to sustainable development by promoting reduced ecological footprints through localized consumption, facilitating resource sharing and reuse, addressing psychological needs for recognition and belonging through social interaction rather than consumption, and encouraging pro-environmental behavior [JH18].

In a local community be it a town, a village, a religious society, or a small family setting, virtually anything has the potential to serve as currency, depending upon the shared understanding among its members that there exist willing recipients ready to accept it in exchange for debt settlement [Gra11]. This is the premise of this paper where we discuss in the following sections how an IOU can be used as a form of local currency within a small community or a family setting.

3 Scenario for Implementation

This segment delves into two scenarios showcasing the use of an IOU as a local currency system. Within these contexts, the scenario introduces characters who play specific roles in the transactions, including Alice, Bob, Charlie, and Dave. These individuals represent loosely coupled mobile systems. By exploring these scenarios, we aim to understand the multifaceted dynamics of small local economies and the diverse means through which transactions occur. Furthermore, the inclusion of characters such as Alice, Bob, Charlie, and Dave serves to facilitate a deeper understanding of the interpersonal interactions inherent in local currency systems. These scenarios highlight the interplay between individuals and their economic transactions, emphasizing the importance of trust in shaping the functioning of local economies.

3.1 Scenario 1

Let us take the first scenario which takes place between two individuals, Alice and Bob. In a simple act of exchange of goods or services between the two, Alice gives her jacket to Bob not seeking a favor in return, but rather hoping for an exchange of something else based on equivalence. This something else could be any material goods or any services that Bob could provide to Alice. Bob decides to express his gratitude by promising something of equal value. This promise takes the form of a casual yet significant IOU, a note that says Bob owes Alice something in return. Both Alice and Bob would be in possession of the IOU which is signed by them and mentions the details of the transaction, be it goods or services. This IOU is a symbol of trust and mutual understanding. Alice, in accepting the IOU, believes in Bob's word and is willing to wait for the promise to be fulfilled. Now, when Bob has something valuable or useful that he can offer in return, he can redeem the IOU. The IOU is redeemed either by giving back any goods of equivalent value that Alice is in need of or by providing any kind of services that Alice would be in need of. Bob could redeem the IOU at once or alternatively, over a period of time by giving Alice multiple goods or services of smaller value. In such a case, as Bob fulfills the IOU, either in one comprehensive transaction or gradually over time, entries are made in the IOU held by both Alice and Bob to reflect the ongoing exchange. These goods or services could be mutually decided and agreed upon by both Alice and Bob. Once the value of the IOU in its entirety has been redeemed, the IOU is said to be closed or nulled. This IOU that results from a simple act of exchange sets the stage for a unique form of currency.

3.2 Scenario 2

In an extension of the previously discussed scenario, we examine a situation where Alice, after receiving an IOU from Bob, opts to transfer it to a third party, Charlie, to whom Alice has a previously outstanding debt. This alteration in the dynamic results in Charlie becoming the recipient of the IOU, and concurrently, Bob incurs a debt to Charlie equivalent to the IOU's stated value. This sequential progression initiates a chain of reciprocal IOU transactions, with participants sometimes navigating the dual roles of creditor and debtor. In the next phase, if Charlie, now holding the IOU, decides to conduct a transaction with another member of the community, say Dave, by acquiring a jacket from him, a further layer of complexity is introduced. Dave facilitates this transaction by accepting the IOU from Charlie, thereby affirming the creditworthiness of Bob, the original debtor. Theoretically, the continued circulation of these IOUs within the community is dependent upon the sustained faith in Bob's unwavering commitment to meeting his financial obligations. It is pivotal to note that the IOU's functionality as a local currency hinges on Bob not paying the settlement of his debt.

3.3 The Actors Involved

In Scenario 1, the main actors involved are Alice and Bob. Alice acts as the creditor, providing goods or services to Bob without seeking an immediate return. Bob, in turn, becomes the debtor by accepting the goods or services and promising to repay Alice with something of equivalent value in the future. The IOU serves as a tangible representation of Bob's debt to Alice, with both parties agreeing to its terms and conditions. As Bob fulfills his promise by redeeming the IOU through either goods or services, the roles of creditor and debtor cease to exist between Alice and Bob.

In Scenario 2, the dynamics expand to include additional actors such as Charlie and potentially Dave. Alice, having initially been involved in IOU transaction with Bob, was a creditor to Bob and also a debtor to Charlie based on a previous debt. By transferring the IOU to Charlie, Alice shifts the creditor role to Charlie. If Charlie further engages in transactions with Dave using the IOU, Dave becomes part of the creditor-debtor network, affirming Bob's creditworthiness. Throughout these exchanges, the actors navigate the dual roles of creditor and debtor, with the continued circulation of IOUs depending on their trust in Bob. This scenario illustrates the interconnected nature of local economies and the reliance on mutual trust among community members to sustain the functioning of IOUs as a form of local currency.

3.4 Where can it be used?

This unique form of local currency can find application in various settings, particularly within closely-knit social structures such as small village communities, familial units, and closely connected households. The scenario presented between Alice and Bob exemplifies its potential within individual interactions within small communities, where everyone has a degree of familiarity with each other. Within these intimate settings characterized by interpersonal familiarity and mutual acquaintance, the operational dynamics of such a form of local currency can seamlessly integrate. The effectiveness of this local currency system is dependent upon the ability of participants to keep track of transactions and maintain a level of trust. Any divergence from established norms or failure to honor commitments carries the risk of undermining trust and social reputation. While also scalable to dispersed communities, it may encounter challenges in larger, more complex urban settings where keeping track of numerous transactions becomes demanding.

3.5 Advantages and Disadvantages

The implications of employing simple bonds or IOUs as a local currency are multifaceted. On the positive side, it fosters a sense of trust and mutual understanding between participants. The IOU can become a symbol of commitment, and its redemption reinforces the reciprocal nature of the relationship. The flexibility in the redemption process, allowing for gradual fulfillment or comprehensive transactions, adds versatility to this system.

However, challenges exist. Scaling this system to accommodate the diverse transactions of a medium-sized community presents logistical hurdles. The need for a significant number of IOUs raises questions about the financial capacity of the initial issuer. Additionally, the system relies heavily on the ongoing commitment of participants to fulfill their promises, and any breach of trust could disrupt the functioning of such a local currency.

Overall, this form of local currency, initiated by simple exchanges and embodied in IOUs, introduces a dynamic economic model based on trust and reciprocal relationships. While its effectiveness is notable in smaller, closely-knit communities, challenges arise in scaling it to larger, more complex settings. The balance between trust, commitment, and logistical feasibility shapes the advantages, and disadvantages of an IOU as a local currency system.

4 Algorithm for the IOU

4.1 Structure of an IOU

The IOU structure encompasses essential elements to document the details of an IOU. It starts with a header containing basic information such as the Name and a unique identification number, followed by Date and Time details when the IOU was issued and then the identification of the parties involved. The specifics of the transaction are also articulated which includes details about the goods or services exchanged, its value the date of exchange, and then comes the terms and conditions, including redemption details. Optionally, a witness section can be included for added authentication. The IOU's status and history section helps track its progression, and space is provided for any additional terms that may be relevant to the specific transaction.

1. Header:

- **Title:** IOU
- **IOU Number:** [Unique Identifier]

2. Timestamp:

- **Date:** [Date of Issuance]
- **Time:** [Time of Issuance]

3. Parties Involved:

- **Creditor's Name:** [Alice]
- **Debtor's Name:** [Bob]
- **Third Party (if applicable):** [Charlie]

4. Transaction Details:

- **Description of Goods/Services Exchanged:** [Description of the exchanged item, e.g.:- jacket]
- **Value Amount (Optional):** [Monetary value or equivalent value of the goods/services]
- **Date of Exchange:** [Date when the exchange occurred]
- **Time of Exchange:** [Time when the exchange occurred]

5. Terms and Conditions:

- **Terms of Redemption:** [Conditions and terms agreed upon for redemption]

- **Redemption Period:** [If applicable, specify any time frame for redemption]

6. IOU Status and History:

- **Current Status:** [Open/Redeemed/Closed]
- **Redemption Entries:** [Record of entries for each redemption, including date and details]

7. Additional Terms (if applicable):

- Any additional terms or exceptions agreed upon by the parties.

4.2 Lifecycle of an IOU

The lifecycle of an IOU, functioning as a form of local currency, typically involves three distinct stages: IOU Creation, Transfer of IOU between involved parties (referred to as Alice and Bob), and Deletion of the IOU upon its redemption or transfer to a different party.

1. IOU Creation

The inception of an IOU commences with its creation, which is initiated by an exchange of goods or services between involved parties. For instance, consider a scenario where Alice gives her jacket to Bob in exchange for a commitment of equivalent value. Subsequently, the IOU is generated, containing crucial details mentioned in the structure of IOU such as the timestamp of issuance, the identities of the parties involved (Alice as the creditor and Bob as the debtor), a comprehensive description of the exchanged item (in this instance, a jacket), and any supplemental terms or conditions. Alice marks the status of the IOU as open, thereby ensuring its usage as a form of local currency.

2. Transfer of IOU

Following the creation of the IOU, it undergoes transfer between parties such as Alice and Bob as described in Scenario 1. Facilitating this transfer securely requires the hashing of the created IOU using a cryptographic hash function like SHA-256. This process generates a unique hash value representing the transaction data. Additionally, encryption of this hashed value is generated using Alice's private key to create Alice's digital signature that authenticates the transaction. A Digital Signature Algorithm such as The Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) can be used for this purpose. On receiving the signed IOU from Alice, Bob verifies Alice's digital signature using her public key thus verifying the transaction's authenticity. Upon successful

verification, the transaction is duly recorded in the IOU's historical log. Conversely, should Bob or Alice opt to transfer the IOU to a third party, such as Charlie, for the settlement of a previous debt, the IOU is transferred accordingly, and its details are updated to reflect the transaction. For instance, if we consider Scenario 2 where the IOU is transferred from Alice to Charlie, in such an instance, Charlie will be the new creditor and Alice will no longer hold possession of the IOU. The status of the IOU in such scenario would still be Open.

3. Deletion of the IOU

The life cycle of an IOU terminates with its deletion, which happens upon its redemption or transfer to another party. In the event that Bob fulfills his debt obligation by returning the jacket to Alice or providing an equivalent value or a service as described in Scenario 1, the IOU is said to be redeemed. The status of the IOU would be Redeemed, then Closed after which it would be deleted by both Alice and Bob. In Scenario 2, the process continues as the IOU is transferred to different people within the local community. Ultimately, upon the fulfillment of its intended purpose or when it ceases to be in circulation, the IOU is Closed and then erased from records, denoting the conclusion of its life cycle.

4.3 Algorithms in IOU

Creating a secure IOU to be shared between Alice and Bob would involve a combination of cryptographic algorithms, including SHA-256 for hashing and a version of Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA) such as Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) for ensuring data integrity and authenticity. This combined use of SHA-256 and ECDSA ensures that the IOU document is tamper-proof, as any alterations to the transaction data would result in a different hash value, rendering the digital signature invalid during verification. The use of digital signatures also ensures the authenticity of the sender, as only the private key owner can generate a valid signature using their private key, which can be verified using their public key. The algorithms are described in the following subsections for hashing and signing the IOU document.

4.3.1 SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm

A Hash, also referred to as message digest, is a super-condensed representation of a message's content, generated through a hashing algorithm. The original message is used as an input to the hashing algorithm, which generates an output known as hash value. The hashing algorithm converts data

of any length into a value of a fixed length, and the fixed length varies based on the algorithm. Hash functions generate a unique value that represents the data in the original message but cannot be reversed. Owing to this reason it is a one-way function. Having access to the hashed value does not enable one to identify the content of the original message i.e. the input. However, possessing both the original message and its hashed value permits verification that the message remains unaltered since the initial hash was generated. This verification process involves producing a new hash from the original message and comparing it with the original hashed value. If the two hashes match, it confirms that the hash function operated on the same input data, thus indicating that the input data remains unchanged. The derivation of a hash value from an ideal hash function is exceptionally challenging, if not impossible, and the likelihood of two distinct messages yielding the same hash value is very low. However, instances in which a hash function yields identical hash values for two distinct inputs are known as Collisions, and the presence of collisions usually results in the disapproval of the hashing algorithm.

Message Digest 5 (MD5) was a very popular and most used algorithm that was developed as a hashing function. However, a vulnerability was identified subsequently which found it to be susceptible to collisions. This led to its classification as "cryptographically broken" by both private and public institutions globally.

SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm or the Secure Hash Algorithm - 256 Algorithm is more secure than MD5 and widely used in digital signatures. This algorithm accepts data of any length and generates a 256-bit long hash value. SHA-256 is widely used for its balance of speed and security. It generates a unique hash value of 256 bits, irrespective of the size of the input message. The SHA-256 algorithm functions through a series of iterative rounds, where each round involves a set of logical and arithmetic operations applied to both the input message and the intermediate hash values. These operations include bitwise logical operations, modular addition, and circular shifts, which are crucial for processing the data effectively. The algorithm's complexity arises from its ability to perform these operations iteratively, refining the hash value with each round. The algorithm is segmented into four distinct parts [Red+21]. The resulting hash value is a 256-bit binary string, often represented in hexadecimal format. The SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm demonstrates key attributes of an effective hashing algorithm. It generates unique hash values for original messages, making it computationally infeasible to derive the original data from the hash. Moreover, it ensures that different messages yield distinct hash codes, thereby preventing hash collisions. Any alteration in the original message results in a substantial modification

to the hash code, reinforcing the algorithm's robustness in detecting changes [Kie+21].

4.3.2 The Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA)

The DSA (Digital Signature Algorithm) was proposed in August 1991 by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and specified in a U.S. Government Federal Information Processing Standard (FIPS 186 [70]) known as the Digital Signature Standard (DSS). DSA is an asymmetric key cryptography algorithm that utilizes two keys: a private key and a public key. It has two main purposes: message signing and message validity authentication (verification) [JMV01]. The use of DSA for digital signature generation is no longer approved by the FIPS. However, it can still be used to verify signatures made prior to the effective date of the standard [Nat23].

Elliptic Curve cryptography

Any elliptic curve can be defined by the following equation [Aqe10]:

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$$

In this equation, x , y , a , and b denote real numbers. Every elliptic curve is associated with an elliptic curve group, comprising the points residing on the curve along with the point O , located at infinity. The elliptic curve group operation involves adding two points, (P and Q), within the same elliptic curve group, denoted as

$$P + Q$$

This problem could also involve multiplication by assuming that Q is a multiple of P :

$$Q = xP$$

It is extremely hard to find x , even if P and Q are already known. This difficult problem, known as the elliptic curve discrete logarithm problem, forms the basis of elliptic curve cryptography.

The Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) is the elliptic curve version of the Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA). Elliptic curves offer two key cryptographic properties. Firstly, they exhibit symmetry about the X-axis, making the top and bottom portions mirror images of each other. Secondly, any straight line intersects the curve in at most three points. Leveraging these properties, a "dot" function can be defined, where two points on the curve yield a third point on the flip side. Figure 9 illustrates $P \text{ dot } Q =$

R, where tracing the line through P and Q identifies their third intersection point on the curve (or between them), and dropping down to point R mirrors it below the X-axis. This process can be iterated; for instance, R dot P produces a point to the left and above Q. Repeating this "dot" operation with the original point P n times (for a suitably large n) results in a point that's highly resistant to guessing or brute-force attacks without knowledge of n, making it a robust one-way function [Aqe10].

Figure 9: Elliptic Curve Cryptosystem (ECC)

An elliptic curve cryptosystem (ECC) is a type of public key cryptosystem that uses a special kind of mathematical curve, along with a prime number and a specific point on that curve, to create encryption keys. These keys consist of a private key and a corresponding public key. The public key is calculated by repeatedly adding the chosen point on the curve to itself a certain number of times, as specified by the private key. However, the process of computing the private key from the public key is a task proven to be exceedingly challenging which involves solving a complex mathematical problem called the elliptic curve discrete logarithm function. This attribute enhances ECC's status as an exceptionally secure encryption method, consequently ensuring the security of the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA).

4.4 IOU as a Currency

The utilization of IOUs as a currency alternative underscores the flexible and adaptable nature of economic exchange mechanisms, particularly within localized communities. IOU as a currency holds value not only as a tangible

asset but also as a symbol of trust and obligation. The fusion of intrinsic value with the function of an IOU enhances the credibility of money, rendering it more resilient to counterfeiting or manipulation [Gra11].

4.4.1 Utilizing IOU as Local Currency: Scenario 1

This subsection describes the context of using an IOU ledger document as a local currency between Alice and Bob as per Scenario 1 described in Section 3.1. The process involves creating one IOU, which is digitally signed by both Alice and Bob. Here's a detailed explanation:

- 1. IOU Generation**

Alice initiates the process by generating a digital IOU ledger document, detailing all the contents regarding the transaction that occurs with Bob.

- 2. Hash of the IOU**

Alice hashes the IOU using the SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm.

- 3. Digital Signature by Alice**

Alice encrypts the hashed IOU using her private key which in turn generates Alice's digital signature. This signature serves as Alice's commitment to the specified terms. ECDSA is used for this purpose ensuring the integrity and authenticity of the document. Alice attaches the original IOU along with the digitally signed IOU and encrypts both these using Bob's public key.

- 4. Transmission to Bob**

Alice sends this encrypted IOU to Bob through a secure communication channel.

- 5. Verification by Bob**

Bob receives the encrypted IOU from Alice. He first decrypts the entire encrypted document using his private key, upon which he gets the original IOU and Alice's digital signature. He decrypts Alice's digital signature using Alice's public key. He verifies the contents of the IOU and copies it into a new IOU to create his copy of the IOU. He then hashes the original IOU using the same SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm to get a hash value which he compares with already hashed IOU that was obtained on decrypting Alice's digital signature. If the two hashes match, he can be assured that the IOU was indeed sent by Alice.

6. **Digital Signature by Bob**

Upon receiving the IOU and verifying its authenticity, Bob reviews the terms and, if in agreement, digitally signs the document using his private key. Bob's signature indicates his acknowledgment and acceptance of the debt. Again, he encrypts his digitally signed IOU and the original IOU with Alice's public key.

7. **Return to Alice**

Bob sends the encrypted IOU back to Alice who also verifies it. The document now bears both Alice's and Bob's digital signatures, symbolizing mutual consent and commitment to the specified terms.

8. **Copy Retention by Bob**

Bob retains a copy of the digitally signed IOU with himself. This copy serves as a ledger entry and proof of the transaction. It includes the digital signatures of both parties, making it tamper-evident.

9. **Verification of Signatures**

In subsequent transactions related to the owed amount, both Alice and Bob can verify the authenticity of the IOU by checking each other's digital signatures. This process adds a layer of trust to the local currency system.

The entire process described above is illustrated in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10: IOU as a Currency - Scenario 1

The digitally signed IOU now functions as a local currency between Alice and Bob. Either party can reference the IOU for the owed value and terms. The document serves as a trustworthy record of the debt.

4.4.2 Utilizing IOU as Local Currency: Scenario 2

In Scenario 2 as described in Section 3.2. where Alice wishes to transfer the IOU to Charlie, establishing a sequential chain of IOU transactions, the steps described below is followed. This process ensures the continuation of the IOU's functionality as a local currency. The subsequent explanation outlines the transfer from Alice to Charlie, with Bob's continued involvement:

1. IOU Transfer from Alice to Charlie

Alice, who is the current creditor of the IOU, opts to transfer it to Charlie for various reasons, such as resolving a prior debt owed to him. Alice and Charlie reach an agreement on the terms of the IOU transfer. These terms can include the new debtor-creditor relationship, any associated conditions, and specific stipulations, all of which are duly amended and

recorded in the IOU document before the transfer initiation. Alice then initiates the transfer.

2. Hash of the IOU

Alice hashes the IOU using the SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm.

3. Digital Signature by Alice

Alice digitally signs the hashed IOU using her private key using ECDSA Algorithm. She then attaches the original IOU with the digitally signed IOU. Alice attaches the original IOU along with the digitally signed IOU and encrypts both these using Charlie's public key.

Alice encrypts the hashed IOU using her private key which in turn generates Alice's digital signature. This signature serves as Alice's commitment to the specified terms and also ensures the integrity and authenticity of the document. Alice attaches the original IOU along with the digitally signed IOU and encrypts both these using Charlie's public key.

4. Transmission to Charlie

Alice securely transmits the encrypted IOU to Charlie through a secure communication channel.

5. Verification by Charlie

Charlie receives the encrypted IOU from Alice. He first decrypts the entire encrypted document using his private key, upon which he gets the original IOU and Alice's digital signature. He decrypts Alice's digital signature using Alice's public key. He verifies the contents of the IOU and copies it into a new IOU to create his copy of the IOU. He then hashes the original IOU using the same SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm to get a hash value which he compares with already hashed IOU that was obtained on decrypting Alice's digital signature. If the two digests match, he can be assured that the IOU was sent by Alice.

6. Digital Signature by Charlie

Next Charlie digitally signs the IOU using his private key. This signature signifies Charlie's acknowledgment and acceptance of the transferred debt.

7. Transmission to Bob

Charlie then encrypts this digitally signed IOU using Bob's public key and sends the encrypted IOU to Bob through a secure communication channel.

8. **Verification by Bob**

Bob receives the encrypted IOU from Charlie. He first decrypts the entire encrypted document using his private key, upon which he gets the original IOU and Charlie's digital signature. He decrypts it using Charlie's public key, upon which he has both the hashed IOU and the original IOU. He verifies the contents of the updated IOU that primarily has new creditor and debtor relationship. He then hashes the IOU using the same SHA-256 Hashing Algorithm to compare it with already hashed IOU that was included in Charlie's digital signature. He then compares the hash he received from Charlie with the hash he computed himself. If the two digests match, he can be assured that the IOU was sent by Charlie.

9. **Digital Signature by Bob**

Upon receiving the IOU, Bob reviews the terms and, if in agreement, digitally signs the document using his private key. Bob's signature indicates his acknowledgment and acceptance of the debt.

10. **Return to Charlie**

Bob sends the digitally signed IOU back to Charlie. The document now bears both Charlie's and Bob's digital signatures, symbolizing mutual consent and commitment to the specified updated IOU.

The updated IOU now reflects Bob's debt to Charlie, which serves as a ledger entry and proof of the transaction. It includes the digital signatures of both Charlie and Bob, making it tamper-evident.

The entire process described above is illustrated in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11: IOU as a Currency - Scenario 2

The IOU, now with both Charlie and Bob's digital signature and Bob's incurred debt, can continue circulating within the community. It remains dependent on the community's sustained faith in Bob's commitment to meeting his financial obligations.

Advantages of IOU

1. **Simplicity:** An single IOU document simplifies the process, reducing the need for multiple documents.
2. **Mutual Consent:** Both parties actively participate in the creation and signing of the IOU, reinforcing mutual consent.
3. **Tamper-Evidence:** The digital signatures on the IOU enhance tamper-evidence, providing a secure and verifiable record.
4. **Ease of Implementation:** In contrast to the intricate and complex technological requirements of Blockchain, the IOU implementation outlined in this paper offers a simpler approach to implementation.

4.5 Distribution of Public Keys

In the case of the IOU as a local currency, as mentioned earlier that the IOU that is created and then digitally signed with the senders private key. Now in order for the receiver to decrypt the signature, they would require the senders public key. One of the most significant challenges in implementing encryption lies in the secure distribution of public keys among communicating parties. This paper explores few primary methods that could be used for the secure exchange of public keys: Offline distribution, Digital Certificates, and the Diffie–Hellman key exchange algorithm.

4.5.1 Offline Distribution

Offline distribution emerges as a straightforward approach for exchanging public keys within the context of utilizing IOUs as a currency in small-scale communities or family settings. The parties engaged in the IOU exchange can meet at a predetermined location. For instance, within a family environment, individuals may gather in a communal area like a living room to exchange their respective public keys. In a community setting, a secure community hall or a secluded venue could serve as the meeting point. This method may also entail the physical exchange of key material, wherein both parties furnish each other with a tangible medium containing the public key. Such mediums could encompass a sheet of paper or a storage device resembling an electronic key.

Offline distribution is particularly well-suited for small, close-knit communities or familial settings characterized by mutual trust among participants.

Despite its apparent simplicity, offline distribution may harbor inherent vulnerabilities. Keying material transmitted through conventional channels may be susceptible to interception risks. For instance, face-to-face meetings could potentially expose the exchange to third-party eavesdropping or secretive recording. Additionally, the physical nature of paper documents or devices heightens the risk of inadvertent loss or theft, thereby compromising the security of the cryptographic process.

4.5.2 Community-Led Digital Certificate Verification System

The use of Digital Certificates for sharing public keys addresses some of the issues associated with offline distribution, providing a more efficient alternative. This paper considers 2 cases on how the digital certificates could be used for sharing the public keys of the members in the case of IOU as a form of local currency.

1. Certificate Authority

A Certificate Authority (CA) serves as a reliable intermediary that verifies the identity of an entity, issues a digital certificate attesting to that identity, and subsequently digitally signs the certificate to ensure its integrity. By affixing its digital signature, the CA effectively links the identity of the subject to their public key, assuming responsibility for verifying the subject's authenticity. This trusted third party, the CA, facilitates secure communication between individuals who may not have prior acquaintance. For instance, in a scenario where Alice wishes to securely communicate with Bob despite never having met him, and both individuals place trust in the same CA, Alice can obtain Bob's digital certificate which contains his public keys to initiate the secure communication process. In order to acquire a digital certificate from a respected Certificate Authority (CA), individuals are required to provide their identity details to the CA's satisfaction. The reliability and credibility of the certificates issued by a CA are contingent upon the level of trust invested in the CA itself. While it may be uncommon for individuals within a local community to be unfamiliar with one another or have not met one another, nevertheless the utilization of CAs remains a viable consideration for using digital certificates for securely exchanging public keys among community members.

2. Community Leader or Elder

In a local community or a family setting where trust is deeply ingrained, the role of a Community Leader or Elder can be pivotal in implementing a digital certificate verification system. Such a trusted individual could potentially act as an internal Certificate Authority (CA) to issue digital certificates within the community. This process aims to ensure secure communication among community members while leveraging the authority and familiarity that the leader possesses. In this approach, the Elder assumes a role similar to that of a Certificate Authority (CA) but holds a unique position as the most trusted member of the community. To obtain a digital certificate, community members approach the Elder, who acts as the central authority overseeing this process. The community member who wishes to be involved in a transaction using the local IOU approaches the elder who verifies their identity ensuring that they align with the community's values and norms. Since the local community or family is trust-based, the elder takes the member's public key and embeds that in a certificate, and signs the certificate using his private key. The elder then provides his public key to the member who can then use it to verify any digital certificates that the elder issues during IOU transaction. Whenever a dispute arises or there is a need for validation, community members can consult the Elder, who possesses the authority to also verify the legitimacy of the digital certificates.

4.5.3 Diffie–Hellman Key Exchange Algorithm

A key exchange algorithm called Diffie-Hellman could be used in certain scenarios where neither Digital Certificates nor offline distribution proves adequate. In such scenarios, Diffie–Hellman proves to be an alternative mechanism by addressing the challenges posed by physical constraints and the absence of Digital Certificates. Diffie–Hellman algorithm can work as a valuable mechanism facilitating secure public key exchange between parties.

The Diffie–Hellman algorithm is a key exchange method that enables two parties to generate a shared secret key over an insecure communication channel. The distinctive feature of this algorithm lies in its capability to facilitate the creation of a shared secret known to both users without the actual transmission of that secret. The efficacy of the Diffie-Hellman algorithm relies on the challenge associated with computing discrete logarithms [RA17].

The functioning of the Diffie–Hellman algorithm is grounded in the mathematics of prime numbers. Consider the scenario where Alice and Bob aim to communicate securely over different locations without a pre-shared key. Instead of directly creating such a key, which could be vulnerable to eaves-

dropping, they employ the Diffie–Hellman algorithm, following this sequence [RA17]:

1. Alice and Bob agree on two large numbers, p (a prime number), and g (an integer), satisfying $1 < g < p$.
2. Alice selects a large random integer r and computes $R = g^r \pmod p$.
3. Bob selects a large random integer s and computes $S = g^s \pmod p$.
4. Alice sends R to Bob, and Bob sends S to Alice.
5. Alice calculates $K = S^r \pmod p$.
6. Bob calculates $K = R^s \pmod p$.

At this juncture, both Alice and Bob possess the same value K , which serves as the basis for secure key communication between the two parties. Now, using this symmetric key, Alice and Bob can exchange their respective public keys with each other. Alice will encrypt her public key using this symmetric key, K and send it to Bob. Bob will decrypt the encrypted message from Alice using the same symmetric key, K to obtain her public key. Although this approach may seem redundant in a close-knit local community or familial context where trust is implicit, it still presents itself as an alternative mechanism in worst-case scenarios. In environments where interpersonal relationships foster a high degree of trust, the need for symmetric key-based encryption may be diminished. However, its utilization offers an additional layer of security and can be a viable option even within trust-based communities.

4.6 Challenges and Solutions in Digital Certificate Verification for IOU Transactions

In certain situations, instances may arise wherein a digital certificate cannot undergo verification, or if the public key of the issuer remains inaccessible. In such scenarios, Alice, Bob, or Charlie may resort to employing subsequent strategies to navigate and resolve these challenges.

1. Alternative Verification Methods

In the absence of the ability to verify a digital certificate, the parties involved can explore alternative methods for confirming the authenticity of the certificate or the identity of the issuer. This may involve cross-referencing the information provided in the certificate with other trusted sources or conducting additional verification steps, such as contacting the issuer directly through alternative communication channels.

2. Peer Validation

In a decentralized context, where trust is established through peer-to-peer relationships, Alice, Bob, or Charlie may opt for peer validation mechanisms. This involves seeking validation from other members of the community who have previously interacted with the issuer or who possess relevant knowledge about the issuer's identity and credibility.

4.7 Solving Double Spending Problem

In the context of a small local community or family network, the use of IOUs as a local currency presents a solution to the double spending problem through the application of digital signatures and hashing techniques. Several strategies can be used to address this challenge effectively.

Firstly, the implementation of immutable transaction records is crucial. Each transaction undergoes verification and is subsequently recorded in a IOU digital ledger maintained collectively by all the members involved in the transaction. This ledger serves as a comprehensive document, documenting every details such as the parties involved, transaction information, and timestamps, thus ensuring transparency and accountability.

Furthermore, the integrity of these transaction records is upheld through the use of cryptographic hashing algorithms like SHA-256. Each entry in the digital ledger undergoes hashing, generating a unique hash value that functions as a digital fingerprint, facilitating data integrity and safeguarding against tampering or manipulation.

Moreover, the inherent trust and familiarity among the members within the local community or family setting foster a system of member oversight. With active engagement from trusted members, any discrepancies or irregularities in transaction records can be promptly identified and addressed, reinforcing the security and reliability of the system.

By combining these methods, an IOU-based local currency system can effectively mitigate the double spending problem, ensuring the integrity, security, and trustworthiness of transactions within the community or family network.

4.8 Consequences of Debt Default

In a trust-based community or familial setting where the interpersonal trust holds significant weight, the failure to fulfill a debt obligation owed through an IOU may result in various forms of social repercussions rather than legal penalties. The following list includes likely social sanctions for non-payment of debts within such a local community framework.

1. **Loss of Trust and Goodwill**

By reneging on their debt, the individual may lose the trust and goodwill of other community members. This loss of trust can have long-term implications for their relationships and interactions within the community.

2. **Social Shaming**

The individual who fails to repay the debt may face social ostracism or condemnation from other members of the community. Their reputation within the community may suffer, leading to a loss of respect.

3. **Exclusion from Community Activities**

The community may decide to exclude the individual from certain local community activities or events as a form of punishment for their failure to fulfill their obligations.

4.9 IOU Attacks

Man in the Middle (MITM) Attack

In the scenario of transmitting the IOU between Alice and Bob, a man-in-the-middle (MITM) attack could occur when an unauthorized individual, identified as Mallory, intercepts the IOU transmitted between Alice and Bob. Mallory strategically positions himself between Alice and Bob, monitoring all details of the IOU transmission between them.

The sequence of events in this attack that could occur are as follows:-

1. **Interception of Communication**

Mallory intercepts the transmission of the digitally signed IOU from Alice to Bob. He gains unauthorized access to the communication channel and eavesdrops on the data being exchanged.

2. **Impersonation of Alice**

Mallory responds to Bob's requests, posing as Alice. He establishes a secure session with Bob, pretending to be Alice. Bob, unaware of Mallory's presence, believes he is communicating directly with Alice.

3. **Secure Session with Bob**

Meanwhile, Mallory establishes a second secure session with Alice, again posing as Bob. Alice, thinking she is communicating with Bob, unknowingly interacts with Mallory.

4. **Interception and Manipulation**

Mallory now "sits in the middle" of the communication between Alice and Bob. He can intercept, modify, or even block the transmission of the IOU. Mallory may alter the terms of the IOU, change the amounts, or insert fraudulent details, deceiving both Alice and Bob.

5. **Unauthorized Access**

By intercepting and manipulating the communication between Alice and Bob, Mallory gains unauthorized access to sensitive information, compromising the confidentiality and integrity of the transaction.

To safeguard against the risk of a man-in-the-middle attack, it is imperative that Alice and Bob utilize secure communication channels and implement cryptographic methods like digital signatures and encryption. It is crucial to emphasize that the cryptographic algorithms employed must be up-to-date to mitigate potential security vulnerabilities. By verifying the legitimacy of digital signatures and maintaining vigilance against suspicious activities, the likelihood of detecting and thwarting such attacks during IOU transmission can be increased. In the context of using IOUs as a local currency, employing robust security measures such as the SHA-256 Algorithm for hashing and ECDSA for Digital Signature can offer a heightened level of protection. These methods adhere to industry and government standards for information security, thereby enhancing the overall security posture of the system.

4.10 Feasibility of IOU as currency

The concept of an IOU as a form of local currency holds both promise and challenges, offering a decentralized approach to economic exchange within local communities or family settings. Similar to traditional currencies, IOUs represent a commitment to repay a debt at a later time, but their utilization as a medium of exchange within a specific locality carries unique implications and considerations.

The circulation of IOUs can demonstrate potential viability within limited social constructs, such as a small village community, a family, or a closely-knit common household. In these scenarios, where interpersonal familiarity exists, and individuals are well-acquainted with one another, the mechanisms of such a debt-token system will find a conducive environment. The threat of losing trust within these limited social constructs carries profound implications. In such a scenario, the price to be paid for non-conformity or non-adherence could result in trust being lost in an individual. In small communities or a family setting, that could mean not only the potential exclusion from future transactions or other financial consequences; rather, it could result in

the individuals who fail to honor their commitments, being socially outcast. Additionally, this system might extend its applicability to more dispersed communities, provided there are means for individuals to keep track of each other's transactions.

One of the primary advantages of employing IOUs as local currency lies in their simplicity and flexibility. Unlike national currencies, which are issued and regulated by central authorities, IOUs can be created and exchanged among community members without the need for complex infrastructure or oversight. This inherent flexibility allows communities to tailor their IOU systems to meet their specific needs and circumstances, fostering economic activity in areas where traditional currency may be scarce or inaccessible. Moreover, their functionality extends beyond facilitating the exchange of tangible goods to encompass the acknowledgment and assessment of non-market endeavors, including the interchange of various competencies and services. Additionally, IOU when used as a local currency can play a crucial role in providing access to various goods or services to individuals who are economically disadvantaged. Furthermore, IOUs promote trust within communities. By facilitating transactions based on mutual trust and reciprocal relationships, IOUs strengthen interpersonal connections and foster a sense of collaboration among community members. In this way, IOUs not only serve as a medium of exchange but also contribute to the social fabric of the community, promoting collaboration among its members.

However, the feasibility of employing IOUs as a form of local currency also has its challenges. One significant hurdle is ensuring widespread acceptance and adoption of IOUs within the community. Overcoming skepticism and instilling confidence in the value and reliability of IOUs may require extensive efforts to raise awareness and build trust among community members. Furthermore, the scalability of IOU systems may pose challenges as communities grow and evolve. While IOUs may function effectively in small, close-knit communities, their viability in larger or more diverse populations remains uncertain. Managing the complexity of IOU systems and ensuring equal distribution and circulation of IOUs across larger communities may require careful planning and coordination. Additionally, the lack of formal regulation inherent in IOU systems raises concerns about accountability and dispute resolution. Without clear mechanisms for addressing issues such as fraud or non-payment, there is a risk that trust in the IOU system may erode over time, undermining its effectiveness as a medium of exchange. Addressing these challenges will require a combination of community engagement, regulatory innovation, and technological solutions to realize the full potential of IOUs as a tool for promoting economic resilience and community well-being.

5 Conclusion

The exploration of Digital Bond Exchange Systems or IOUs as a local form of currency within loosely coupled mobile systems has unveiled a significant potential to redefine economic interactions in local communities. Through the analysis of historical forms of money, digital currencies, and the technical feasibility of implementing IOUs without blockchain technology, this research has illuminated the pathways toward achieving economic independence and resilience in small localized settings.

The findings highlight the possibility of IOUs in facilitating transactions within small communities, offering an alternative to traditional financial systems and currencies. The concept extends beyond mere theoretical exploration, presenting practical framework scenarios for communities to establish their localized currency systems, thereby fostering economic empowerment and sustainability. The case scenarios explored in this study highlight the adaptability of digital bonds or IOUs to various local economic contexts, demonstrating their capacity to address specific community needs while enhancing financial inclusiveness. Furthermore, the research addresses the technological considerations essential for the deployment of digital bond systems, including the creation, verification, and management of IOUs. The discussion on cryptographic algorithms, digital signatures and digital certificates elucidates the technical backbone necessary for ensuring the security and integrity of transactions, a crucial aspect for gaining community trust and acceptance of new financial instruments.

Despite the optimistic outlook, the study also acknowledges the need to scale this system from small communities to larger and diverse communities. These include the need for widespread infrastructure development, and overcoming initial resistance to new financial concepts. Moreover, the regulatory landscape presents a significant hurdle, necessitating a delicate balance between innovation and compliance with existing financial laws and guidelines. The conclusion drawn from this research is twofold. Firstly, digital bonds hold promise as a tool for economic revitalization and autonomy in local communities, offering a scalable and secure method for transaction facilitation. Secondly, the successful implementation of such systems requires a collaborative effort among stakeholders, including community members, technologists, and policymakers, to address the technical, social, and regulatory challenges identified.

In essence, this study contributes to the evolving discourse on digital currencies and localized financial systems, laying a foundation for future inves-

tigations into the deployment of non-blockchain-based digital bond exchange systems. The envisioned future is one where communities leverage digital bonds or IOUs to create a sustainable and inclusive economic ecosystem, tailored to their unique needs and aspirations.

The broader implications of this research extend to the field of financial technology and community development, suggesting a paradigm shift towards more decentralized and community-centric economic models. As the world grapples with the limitations of traditional financial systems, the exploration of alternatives like digital bonds or IOUs presents a promising avenue for fostering resilience, inclusiveness, and innovation in local economies. Moving forward, the continued exploration and experimentation will be pivotal in realizing the full potential of digital bonds or IOUs as a transformative tool for local and even global economic landscapes.

Acronyms

IOU: I owe you

BC: Before christ

US: United States

USA: United States of America

UK: United Kingdom

USD: United States Dollars

c.: circa

i.e.: That is

CPU: Central Processing Unit

ICMA: International Capital Market Association

CBDC: Central Bank Digital Currency

CRL: Certificate Revocation List

OCSP: Online Certificate Status Protocol

VR: Viewstamped Replication

BG: Byzantine Generals

POW: Proof of Work

PBFT: Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance

PoS: Proof of Stake

DPoS: Delegated Proof of Stake

PoH: Proof of Humanity

CW-PoW: Compute and Wait in the Proof of Work

CN: Common Name

DN: Distinguished Name

SHA: Secure Hash Algorithm

DSA: Digital Signature Algorithm

ECDSA: Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm

ECC: Elliptic Curve Cryptosystem

MD5: Message Digest 5

API: Application Program Interface

PKI: Public Key Infrastructure

CA: Certificate Authority

RA: Registration Authority

CRL: Certificate Revocation List

CP: Certification Policy

OCSP: Online Certificate Status Protocol

ASCII: American Standard Code for Information Interchange

NIST: National Institute of Standards and Technology

FIPS: Federal Information Processing Standard

MITM: Man in the Middle

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